

Preliminary Optimization of Fuel Bowing Surrogate Variables for the BEAVRS Benchmark

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents three optimization algorithms applied to two surrogate variables designed to mimic the effect of fuel bowing and reproduce the power tilt observed in the BEAVRS benchmark. Surrogates are preferred over high-fidelity multi-physics models to reduce computational complexity and enable efficient optimization. The first model alters the coolant temperature distribution at the assembly inlets, while the second introduces rigid radial displacements of the fuel assemblies. These surrogate variables are implemented in CASMO4E/SIMULATE3 and optimized using hill climbing, simulated annealing, and least squares minimization. Additionally, regularization schemes are developed to avoid overfitting and ensure spatial smoothness of the temperature and displacement fields. The optimized solutions reduce the simulation-to-measurement RMS error from 5.1% to between 1% and 2%, consistent with detector uncertainty.

Keywords: Fuel bowing, Surrogate variables, Optimization algorithms, PWR

1. INTRODUCTION

The BEAVRS benchmark [1] is a 4-loop PWR core benchmark, with in-core detector signals for 58 of the 193 fuel assemblies over the first two operating cycles. At hot zero power conditions the core presents a large radial power tilt (about $\pm 10\%$ between the north-west and south-east quadrants, Figure 1c) despite symmetric geometry and fuel loading. This power tilt is not predicted by traditional neutronics models alone, and a root mean squared error (RMS) of 5.1% is observed between simulation (CASMO/SIMULATE [2] and MC21 [3]) and measurements.

Figure 1. Power tilt observed when comparing axially-integrated detector readings in SIMULATE3 and the benchmark (RR1 is short for detector reaction rates).

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Previous work [2] reproduced the tilt by introducing uneven inter-assembly water gaps. The gap distribution was optimized directly against the measurements, reducing the RMS from 5.1% to 0.7%. However, the method was largely *ad hoc* and the final gap distribution lacked physical interpretation, serving mainly as a correction to match the benchmark rather than an explanation of the underlying phenomenon.

More recent studies [4, 5] indicate that flow asymmetries at core inlet, caused by pump start-up transients, can induce fuel assembly bowing. The resulting mechanical deformation affects coolant flow and local moderation, which in turn produces radial power asymmetries. This suggests that the observed tilt may originate from a coupled sequence: flow asymmetry \rightarrow fuel bowing \rightarrow moderation change \rightarrow power tilt.

The objective of this work is to move from *ad hoc* adjustments toward a physics-informed inference approach, while avoiding the cost of fully coupled multi-physics simulations. In this preliminary study, two simplifying assumptions are adopted. Fluid dynamics is not modeled explicitly and fuel bowing is not solved with structural mechanics. Instead, fuel bowing is represented through surrogate variables chosen to reproduce its impact on neutron moderation, and the study focuses on reproducing the measured radial tilt by optimizing the surrogates against the BEAVRS measurements. The resulting framework provides the neutronic component of a future coupled methodology, where flow calculations will constrain the surrogate variables and enable inference of the inlet conditions responsible for the asymmetry. Although developed for the BEAVRS benchmark, the methodology is general and applicable to other reactor cores.

2. METHODS

2.1. Fuel Bowing Surrogate Variables

Fuel bowing is a 3D phenomenon in which fuel assemblies deform axially into C- or S-shaped curves. This deformation alters the local moderation, producing asymmetries in the neutron flux. Although high-fidelity mechanical models can capture this behavior, coupling structural deformation with neutronics and fluid dynamics would be computationally extremely expensive. To avoid this burden, fuel bowing is approximated using surrogate variables that reproduce its net effect. The BEAVRS 3D detector signals are therefore axially integrated to obtain a 2D radial core map (Figure 1). In this representation, bowing appears as assembly-wise variations in moderator mass within each channel.

This simplification prevents the need for full 3D Monte Carlo simulations. The deterministic codes CASMO4E and SIMULATE3 are used instead¹, allowing for 3D calculations at significantly lower cost. By tuning the surrogate variables, the moderation imbalance (and thus the radial tilt) can be reproduced. The resulting surrogate distributions may also provide information about the underlying asymmetric flow conditions responsible for the deformation.

Two independent surrogates are considered: assembly inlet temperature (affecting coolant density) and rigid assembly displacement (affecting coolant volume).

2.1.1. Assemblies inlet temperature: DLT card

The moderator mass in a channel can be modified by changing its density ρ through its temperature T . A non-uniform radial temperature distribution can therefore mimic the effect of fuel bowing. SIMULATE3 implements this capability via the HYD.DLT card (hereafter DLT), which specify assembly-wise inlet coolant temperature.

¹Open source models of the BEAVRS benchmark are available at <https://github.com/mit-crpg/BEAVRS>
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2.1.2. Assemblies rigid displacement: LDX/LDY cards

Alternatively, the water volume V can be varied by rigidly shifting fuel assemblies. This directly modifies the water gaps between neighboring assemblies. CASMO4E enables this through the LDX and LDY card, which apply pin-level displacements in the x and y directions. When all pins in an assembly are shifted uniformly, the whole assembly undergoes a rigid translation. This approach differs from previous work [2], where only the assembly pitch was changed, producing equal gap variations on all four sides rather than an actual displacement of assemblies.

The inference problem thus reduces to optimizing the DLT and LDX/LDY cards so as to minimize the RMS difference between simulations and measurements while reproducing the observed power tilt.

2.2. Optimization Algorithms

Figure 2 schematically shows the optimization algorithm. At each iteration, the bowing surrogate (DLT or LDX/LDY cards) is perturbed and evaluated in SIMULATE3. The simulated detector signals (RR1) are compared with the measurements using a figure of merit (FOM), which typically combines the RMS error with regularization terms. An acceptance criterion then determines whether the candidate solution is retained before proceeding to the next iteration.

Figure 2. Optimization algorithm for DLT and LDX/LDY cards.

The DLT card is treated as a continuous variable. The same concept applies to the LDX/LDY cards, but these require CASMO4E calculations, which are significantly more expensive than SIMULATE3 runs. For this reason, a precomputed set of assembly displacements is used, where each assembly is tested in nine discrete positions: north, south, east, west, the four diagonal directions, as well as the reference position. Every shift corresponds to a translation of 0.17 cm in the x and/or y directions, the maximum allowed by the geometry. Therefore, the optimization becomes discrete, but with a very large number of possible combinations (9^{193}).

The optimized DLT and LDX/LDY distributions are expected to retain a residual RMS comparable to the measurement uncertainty, estimated in 1-1.5% [2]. Lower values would indicate unphysical overfitting.

Finally, the problem is intrinsically undetermined: the number of unknowns (193 fuel assemblies) greatly exceeds the number of observations (58 detector readings), therefore multiple solutions are

mathematically possible.

2.2.1. Hill climbing

Hill climbing (HC) is an iterative algorithm with a deterministic acceptance rule. It systematically perturbs each element of the DLT matrix by small increments, and accepts the new DLT only if it reduces the FOM. A complete cycle consists of updating all 193 assemblies using a predefined set of perturbation magnitudes, and multiple cycles are performed.

Because HC searches only in the neighborhood of the current solution, it can converge to local minima. To reduce this bias, the initial DLT distribution and the update order of the assemblies are randomized.

A discrete HC variant is applied to the LDX/LDY cards. Instead of continuous perturbations, a randomly selected assembly is evaluated in its nine allowed positions, and the position yielding the lowest FOM is retained.

2.2.2. Simulated annealing

Simulated annealing (SA) is a stochastic optimization algorithm inspired by the physical process of metal cooling. Unlike HC, it can accept solutions with higher FOM, allowing escape from local minima. The probability of accepting a worse solution decreases during the cooling phase as the pseudo-temperature τ is progressively reduced, making the search increasingly greedy.

The acceptance probability follows the standard exponential law:

$$P(\tau_n) = \exp\left(-\frac{FOM_{new} - FOM_{best}}{\bar{\tau} \cdot \tau_n}\right) \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\tau}$ normalizes the initial acceptance probability. The pseudo-temperature decreases according to an exponential cooling law:

$$\tau_n = \alpha_1 \cdot \tau_{n-1} = \alpha_1^n \cdot \tau_0 \quad (2)$$

with $\alpha_1 = 0.90$, $\tau_{max} = 100$, $\tau_{min} = 0.01$.

At each iteration the entire DLT map is randomly perturbed. The perturbation magnitude decreases over the cooling phase following a similar exponential decay with rate $\alpha_2 = 0.95$.

An discrete SA variant is used for LDX/LDY: only one assembly at a time is perturbed by selecting among the nine allowed positions.

2.2.3. Least squares minimization

This approach reformulates the problem in linear form as $Ax = b$, where x is the unknown DLT distribution, b is the difference between the detector readings and the symmetric reference solution (Figure 1c), and A is the Jacobian matrix (58x193) relating the response of each detector (58 in total) to a change in DLT (193 free elements). The matrix equation $Ax = b$ is solved using least squares (LSQ) minimizing:

$$\|Ax - b\|_2^2 \propto RMS^2 \quad (3)$$

The Jacobian matrix A is precomputed by perturbing each DLT element independently and recording the resulting change in RR1 at all detector locations. This procedure assumes a locally linear response, meaning the coefficients of A remain approximately constant within the temperature range considered. This assumption is verified through a sensitivity analysis up to ± 30 °F.

Figure 3. RR1 versus DLT at different core locations. The linear dependence confirms the validity of the constant Jacobian approximation.

Because this method relies on derivatives of a continuous variables, it cannot be applied to the discrete LDX/LDY displacements.

2.3. Regularization Schemes

To avoid overfitting and preserve physical realism, the optimized DLT and LDX/LDY distributions must exhibit spatial smoothness. Ideally, such regularity would be constrained by coupled fluid dynamics simulations. Instead, in this work it is enforced through simple regularization applied directly to the surrogate variables.

The simplest approach limits the DLT values within fixed bounds. Typical optimization ranges are ± 10 °F or ± 20 °F, with a limit in ± 30 °F.

For the LDX/LDY cards, regularity is partially inherent: displacements have constant magnitude and vary only in direction, which was found sufficient to maintain spatial smoothness. In contrast, bounding the DLT alone proved inadequate for generating continuous and regular solutions. Therefore, two additional regularization schemes are introduced.

2.3.1. Tikhonov regularization

Tikhonov (L_2) regularization [6] introduces a penalty cost to those DLT solutions with a high L_2 norm:

$$FOM = 58 \cdot RMS^2 + \lambda \cdot \|DLT\|_2^2 \quad (4)$$

The tuning factor λ is a weight between the RMS and $\|DLT\|_2^2$, and was typically set to 10^{-5} .

2.3.2. Total variation regularization

This is a variant of the Tikhonov regularization and specifically enforces continuous solutions through a penalty factor constructed with the total variation (TV) [7] of the temperature field. This factor is an indicator of the total average discontinuity of a DLT map and is defined as:

$$TV = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2 \cdot 193} \sum_{i,j} \sum_{neighbors} (DLT_{i,j} - DLT_{neighbor})^2} \quad (5)$$

Then, the figure of merit changes to:

$$FOM = 58 \cdot RMS^2 + \lambda \cdot 2 \cdot 193 \cdot TV^2 \quad (6)$$

where again λ is a weight factor between RMS and TV, tested between 10^{-7} and 10^{-3} .

3. RESULTS

This section presents some of the optimal solutions generated with the algorithms and identifies important patterns. The initial RMS between symmetric SIMULATE3 and the measurements is 5.1%.

3.1. Optimization of DLT

Figure 4 shows the optimal DLT distributions obtained with unregularized HC, SA and LSQ. All solutions are highly irregular and present a residual RMS well below 1%. Such behavior is unlikely to represent asymmetric flow conditions, highlighting the need for regularization.

Figure 4. Three examples of optimal DLT (in °F) without regularization schemes.

Figure 5 presents DLT maps obtained with Tikhonov and total variation (TV) regularization. Tikhonov improves continuity but still produces a non-physical checkerboard pattern. In contrast, TV regularization effectively removes discontinuities, with the weight λ controlling the trade-off between accuracy and smoothness. The resulting distributions reproduce the north-west to south-east power tilt observed in the measurements, while the residual RMS remains between 1% and 1.7%, well within detector uncertainty. However, excessively large λ over-smooth the solution, making the DLT artificially continuous and masking spatial features. The expected outcome is better reflected in Figure 5c, which exhibits coherent spatial patterns.

Figure 5. Three examples of regularised DLT (in °F) with the least squares method.

3.2. Optimization of LDX/LDY

Figure 6 shows four displacement maps obtained with HC and SA. All reach a residual RMS of about 0.9% and display recurring spatial patterns. These are highlighted in Figure 7, where each arrow represents the mean displacement of an assembly; longer arrows indicate larger average shifts and smaller

variability.

Figure 6. Four examples of LDX/LDY maps. Top row highlights the north-south direction, bottom row the east-west direction.

The averaged map reveals a consistent spatial pattern, with large groups of assemblies exhibiting similar shifts. These structures resemble those observed in Figure 5c, despite being derived from different surrogate variables and regularization schemes. In particular, Figure 6h presents a clear correspondence: assemblies displaced east (yellow) align with negative DLT values, while assemblies displaced west (green) align with positive DLT values.

Figure 7. Average of 60 LDX/LDY maps with recurring patterns.

These low-order spatial modes may be indicative of underlying flow asymmetries and provide a useful

basis for flow condition inference. However, the current regularization schemes are purely mathematical rather than physically derived, motivating the development of physics-informed constraints guided by fluid dynamics simulations.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The leading hypothesis of the large asymmetries observed in the BEAVRS detector measurements is flow-induced fuel bowing. This work links neutron detector signals to potential flow asymmetries using surrogate representations of fuel bowing, avoiding fully coupled high-fidelity simulations. Two surrogate variables are introduced: assembly inlet coolant temperature (DLT card in SIMULATE3) and rigid assembly displacements (LDX/LDY cards in CASMO4E). Three optimization algorithms and two regularization strategies are applied to reproduce the measured power tilt and reduce the RMS error between simulation and measurement—from an initial 5.1% to 1–2%, within detector uncertainty. The resulting DLT and LDX/LDY distributions remain physically reasonable.

A key limitation is the use of manually selected regularization schemes based on assumed deformation patterns. Future work will explore physics-based regularization schemes informed by fluid dynamics simulations, enabling a more robust mathematical framework for inference of reactor flow conditions.

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